

1 Hacking the topographic ruggedness index

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11 Abstract

12 The topographic ruggedness index (TRI) is widely adopted for the analysis of digital elevation
13 models, providing information on local surface spatial variability. In this work, the TRI is
14 interpreted according to a geostatistical perspective, highlighting its main characteristics and
15 drawbacks. TRI can be interpreted as an omnidirectional short-range spatial variability index,
16 computed according to a pixel centered perspective. The simplicity and interpretability of
17 the index, free from user-dependent selections, promoted its implementation in several
18 software environments and its application in a wide set of case studies. However, the index
19 has several drawbacks for its application in earth sciences, such as a strong dependency on
20 local slope (it is basically an average adjacent neighbor slope algorithm) and the selection of
21 different lag distances in the computation of spatial variability along the main directions and
22 the diagonal ones. We propose a new metric radial roughness (RRI) in order to solve the
23 main drawbacks of TRI but maintaining its main philosophy (i.e., pixel centered perspective
24 and simplicity of the algorithm). The new index corrects for the differences in lag distances
25 and resolves the dependency on trend using increments of order 2. The code of the index,
26 implemented in R statistical language, and test data are provided with the paper
27 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7132160>) to promote its implementation in other software
28 environments.

29 Keywords: DEM, ecology, geomorphometry, surface roughness, terrain analysis

30

31 1. Introduction

32 The analysis of surface roughness from digital elevation models (DEMs), analogously to the analysis
33 of image texture from imagery (Haralick et al., 1973), represents a key element in many

34 geoenvironmental, geoengineering and remote sensing applications (e.g., McKean and Roering,
35 2004; Glenn et al., 2006; Wilson et al., 2007; Woodcock et al., 1988, Rózycka et al., 2017). But the
36 possible applications can be broader, including for example ecological applications (e.g., Nelleman
37 and Thomsen, 1994) and the study of distribution of human residential development (Vukomanovic
38 and Orr, 2014). It is not our intention to provide an epistemological discussion on the concept of
39 roughness in earth sciences and on the related terminology. In the context of earth sciences (Shepard
40 et al. 2001; Smith, 2014) and geomorphometry (Pike, 2000; Wilson and Gallant, 2000) there is not a
41 consensus on a definition of roughness, and multiple related terms are frequently adopted, such as
42 "fabric", "ruggedness", "rugosity", "texture", "waviness" and others. Here, surface roughness (further
43 referred for brevity as roughness) is intended as synonym of surface texture and hence it is a complex
44 and multiscale characteristic of a surface' spatial variability. Accordingly, this interpretation deviates
45 from the definition provided in surface metrology (e.g., Leach, 2013), where roughness is referred to
46 short-wavelength surface texture features. When the analysis of roughness is performed on a digital
47 elevation model (DEM), represented as a regular grid (i.e., a raster image), there is a complete
48 algorithmic convergence between image texture and surface texture (Haralick et al., 1973; Woodcok
49 et al. 1988; Atkinson and Lewis, 2000; Ojala et al., 2002; Lucier and Stein 2005; Garrigues et al., 2006;
50 Balaguer et al., 2010; Trevisani et al. 2012). Moreover, the same concepts can be adopted to real 3D
51 surfaces as well as to elevation points clouds (Pollyea and Fairley, 2011), given the proper adaptation
52 of algorithms. It should be also highlighted that with usual DEMs, which are a 2.5D representation of
53 solid earth surface (Burrough and McDonnel, 1998) the roughness computed from them is an
54 apparent roughness, given that this typology of DEM represents the projection of a 3D surface on an
55 horizontal plane.

56 The topographic ruggedness index (TRI, Riley et al., 1999) is a widely adopted measure of short-range
57 roughness. It was initially developed in the context of ecological analysis because many biosphere-
58 related processes are influenced by surface roughness (Nellemann and Thomsen, 1994; Jenness,
59 2004; Sappington, 2007; Wilson et al., 2007; Hagerty et al., 2011). Even though more statistically robust
60 and informative roughness indexes can be considered (e.g., Herzfeld and Higginson, 1996; Trevisani
61 and Rocca, 2015; Trevisani et al. 2023), the approach underlying TRI is still valuable and it is worth
62 trying to improve its drawbacks while keeping its appealing features. TRI is particularly interesting in
63 earth sciences and ecology applications because of its pixel centered perspective in evaluating
64 roughness. Another characteristic that made popular this index is the extreme simplicity of the
65 algorithm (Wilson et al., 2007) that fostered its implementation, efficiently and easily, in multiple
66 software packages, e.g. GRASS GIS (GRASS, 2023), MICRODEM (USNA, 2023), SAGA GIS, Terra
67 package for R (RSPATIAL, 2023), Whitebox (Whitebox Geospatial, 2023), ArcMap (ESRI, 2023), and
68 others. However, TRI has some severe limitations, often leading to a misuse of the index. A first
69 limitation is the strong dependency of the index to local slope, unlike other indexes (Woodcock, 1977;
70 Guth 1999 and 2001; Wilson and Gallant, 2000; Grohmann et al., 2011; Trevisani et al. 2023). Other
71 issues are related to the usage of different pixel distances along the main directions (NS and EW)
72 with respect to the diagonal ones and the use of only 8 samples in the estimation of the index, making
73 it highly sensitive to noise.

74 Accordingly, the main aim of this technical note is to provide a new implementation of the TRI, that
 75 maintains the main philosophy behind it (i.e., simplicity and pixel centered perspective) while
 76 improving its main drawbacks. The presented improvements are based on ongoing research on
 77 geostatistical-based approaches for roughness analysis, that led to the recent implementation of an
 78 efficient and informative geostatistical algorithm (Trevisani and Rocca, 2015; Trevisani et al., 2023;
 79 Trevisani, 2023), capable of highlighting specific aspects of roughness. Moreover, the reanalysis of
 80 TRI from the geostatistical perspective permits highlighting its key features and finding a clear
 81 pathway for its improvement.

82 The implementation provided here refers to the original TRI implementation relying on a 3x3 kernel;
 83 alternative extensions devised for multiscale analysis are not considered. Some approaches, for
 84 example, generalize TRI considering larger kernels with weights or adopt smoothing approaches prior
 85 to the computation (Wilson et al. 2007). These variations are not considered here because they
 86 increase the complexity of the approach, making less convenient its application with respect to other
 87 more flexible and controllable approaches based on geostatistics (e.g., Garrigues et al., 2006;
 88 Balaguer et al., 2010; Trevisani and Rocca 2015; Trevisani et al, 2023). Moreover, the improvements
 89 proposed here can still be adopted for multiscale analysis without modifications, using multilevel
 90 upscaling of the original DEM (e.g., Wilson et al., 2007; Lindsay et al. 2019; Newman et al., 2022). It
 91 should be also noted that the dependence on slope can be filtered out by calculating TRI on a residual
 92 DEM (Guisan et al., 1999; Wilson and Gallant, 2000; Ilich et al., 2021), also known as topographic
 93 position index (TPI). TPI also suffers because it does not consider the different calculation distances
 94 along the diagonals. However, as discussed in Trevisani et al. (2023), there are different approaches
 95 and different calculation parameters that can be selected for deriving the residual DEM, generating
 96 some subjectivity in its derivation. The solution adopted here is unequivocal and the modified index,
 97 as the original one, doesn't require user-based choices, apart from the resolution of the input DEM.

98

99 2. Methodology

100 2.1 TRI according to geostatistics

101 TRI has clear connections with geostatistical spatial variability estimators; in fact, differences between
 102 pixel values separated by a given lag distance (further referred as directional differences, DDs) are
 103 the building blocks of estimators of spatial variability (Isaaks and Srivastava, 1989; Goovaerts, 1997;
 104 Chilès and Delfiner 2012), such as the variogram (eq. 1), the madogram (eq. 2) and the robust version
 105 based on the median of absolute differences (MAD, Trevisani and Rocca, 2015).

$$106 \quad \gamma(\mathbf{h}) = \frac{1}{2N(\mathbf{h})} \sum_{\alpha=1}^{N(\mathbf{h})} [z(\mathbf{u}_{\alpha}) - z(\mathbf{u}_{\alpha} + \mathbf{h})]^2 = 1/2 \frac{1}{N(\mathbf{h})} \sum_{\alpha=1}^{N(\mathbf{h})} \Delta^2(\mathbf{h})_{\alpha} = 1/2 \cdot \text{mean}(\Delta^2(\mathbf{h}))$$

107 (1)

108
$$\gamma(\mathbf{h})_p = \frac{1}{2N(\mathbf{h})} \sum_{\alpha=1}^{N(\mathbf{h})} |z(\mathbf{u}_\alpha) - z(\mathbf{u}_\alpha + \mathbf{h})|^p = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \text{mean}(|\Delta(\mathbf{h})_\alpha|^p) \text{ with } p = 1$$

109
$$(2)$$

110
 111 where $\Delta(\mathbf{h})_\alpha = z(\mathbf{u}_\alpha) - z(\mathbf{u}_\alpha + \mathbf{h})$. In Eqs. (1)-(2), \mathbf{h} is the separation vector (lag) between two
 112 locations (u), $z(\mathbf{u})$ is the value of the variable of interest in the location u (e.g., elevation, residual
 113 elevation, band intensity, etc.), and $N(\mathbf{h})$ is the number of point pairs with a separation vector \mathbf{h}
 114 found in the search window considered. Hence, $\Delta(\mathbf{h})_\alpha = z(\mathbf{u}_\alpha) - z(\mathbf{u}_\alpha + \mathbf{h})$ represents a given DD.

115 The main difference between TRI and geostatistical approaches relies on the way in which the DDs
 116 are sampled from the local spatial domain considered (e.g., search window or kernel, the two terms
 117 are used interchangeably). In the original formulation, TRI is calculated with a 3x3 kernel, considering
 118 the eight differences between the central pixel and the external ones (figure 1 left). Accordingly, it
 119 represents a radial measure of spatial variability. In a usual geostatistical approach (figure 1, right),
 120 with a 3x3 window, the set of included DDs in the estimation would be different and much larger.
 121 Moreover, with the geostatistical approaches adapted to geomorphometry (Trevisani and Rocca
 122 2015; Trevisani et al., 2023) the set of samples is still larger and includes a correction for diagonal
 123 distances. In the examples provided in figure 1, we don't consider the issue of the different lag
 124 distances between main directions and diagonal ones; this topic will be discussed later. Moreover, it
 125 is worth noting that the directional differences of TRI if divided by the lag distances are essentially
 126 (discrete) directional derivatives radiating from the center, and hence related to the divergence.

129 *Figure 1. Example of selection of DDs for TRI (left) and for an hypothetical geostatistical estimator of*
 130 *omnidirectional variability (right). Blue arrows represent directional differences with lags of 1 pixel and*
 131 *the light blue with a lag of $\sqrt{2}$ pixels.*

132
 133 In the original formulation of Riley et al. (1999), TRI is defined as the square root of the sum of the
 134 squared DDs; if normalized by the number of DDs (i.e., divided by 8), it is the square root of the mean
 135 of the squared DDs (eq. 3); accordingly, it is analogous to the square root of the variogram (eq. 1),

136 apart from the division by 2. Ultimately, it provides an omnidirectional measure of spatial variability
137 for a lag distance of 1.207 px, where px is the non-SI unit pixel.

$$138 \quad TRI_{sqr} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{8} \sum_{\alpha=1}^8 \Delta^2(\mathbf{h}_{\alpha})} \quad (3)$$

139
140 An improved version, as implemented in Terra package and in most software, computes the index
141 by means of the absolute value of DDs (e.g. 4, Wilson et al., 2007), given that squared DDs are very
142 sensitive to data contamination. Accordingly, it is like an omnidirectional madogram (eq. 2).

$$143 \quad TRI = \frac{1}{8} \sum_{\alpha=1}^8 |\Delta(\mathbf{h}_{\alpha})| \quad (4)$$

144 The last version is convenient from the interpretative point of view because it provides the mean
145 absolute difference in elevation observed by the central pixel respect to its neighbors. However, the
146 average lag distance is 1.207 px, which is a little unpractical from the interpretative point of view;
147 moreover, the different lag distances can generate various biases with anisotropic features depending
148 on their orientation, wavelengths, and spatial variability characteristics.

149 The evident similarities with geostatistics explain very clearly the dependency of TRI on slope; in fact,
150 in geostatistics, the variables from which to calculate the spatial variability/continuity indexes should
151 be at least in conditions of intrinsic stationarity (Isaaks and Srivastava, 1989). This means that in the
152 considered spatial domain (i.e., a 3x3 window for TRI) there should not be a trend, representing long-
153 range variations. If a trend is present, the estimates of spatial variability would be biased. This is
154 evident with TRI; if this index is applied on a perfectly smooth but sloping face, it will return a non-
155 zero result. In ecological applications the influence of slope can be the intended result; for example,
156 the main factor controlling animal movement could be the overall spatial variability, considering both
157 short-range (the residual) and long-range (the trend) components. However, for most earth sciences
158 related applications, such as for deriving proxies of flow impedance and for geomorphological
159 interpretation, the short-range roughness is the object of the study. For this kind of aim, TRI should
160 not be applied directly to a DEM, otherwise it will represent a proxy of slope more than a measure of
161 short-range roughness (figure 2). For the 2 m resolution DEM represented in figure 2 the correlation
162 between TRI and slope is 0.989. As reported above, one adopted solution the computation of TRI on
163 a detrended surface (Wilson et al. 2007; Ilich et al., 2021); however, the detrending can be performed
164 in different ways and this induces higher complexity and user choices (Trevisani et al., 2023). We
165 present a solution that resolves these issues maintaining the simplicity and the pixel centered
166 perspective of the original algorithm. The current implementation in R is devised for DEMs and
167 imagery represented in a projected coordinate system. For working in geographical coordinates, the
168 algorithm has been adapted in MICRODEM according to the latitude/longitude distance corrections
169 (Guth and Kane, 2021).

170
 171 *Figure 2. Example of contrasting local surface roughness for an Alpine glacial environment (top left:*
 172 *DEM; top right: hillshade). Calculation of conventional TRI (bottom right) highlighting the strong*
 173 *dependence on slope (bottom left). The 2 m resolution DEM has been derived from an airborne Lidar*
 174 *survey (Trentino, Italy). Color scales for slope and TRI are histogram equalized.*

175
 176 2.2 The modified algorithms

177 Accordingly, we present two main modifications of TRI original formulation (eq. 4) that, while
 178 maintaining the simplicity of the original approach, remove the effect of slope and correct for
 179 different lag distances. These modifications lead to the definition of a short-range radial roughness
 180 index (RRI). The algorithms are implemented in R using the "Terra" library (RSPATIAL; 2023). However,
 181 the algorithms can be implemented easily in any GIS and image analysis environment; the code and
 182 test data provided should serve as the basis for implementing it in any environment. For example,
 183 these have been also implemented in the open source software MICRODEM, written in the Delphi
 184 (object Pascal) language (Guth, 2023).

185 In terms of software implementation, referring to the layout of pixels indexing for 3x3 kernel in figure
 186 3, the pseudocode of conventional TRI can be expressed as:

187
$$TRI = \frac{1}{8} \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ i \neq 5}}^9 |z_i - z_5| \quad (5)$$

188 that is the mean of absolute difference between the central pixel and its eight surroundings.

189

190

191 *Figure 3. Pixels indexing layout for 3x3 kernels adopted for representing the pseudocode of TRI.*

192

193 2.2.1 TRI_{k2} : removing the influence of local slope

194 The impact of local slope/trend can be filtered out with the same approach based on increments of
 195 order-k used in geostatistics (Chilès and Delfiner, 2012) and recently implemented in the algorithm
 196 for roughness analysis of Trevisani et al. (2023). In fact, the detrending can be avoided by exploiting
 197 the capability of increments (in this case differences) of order K to filter out a polynomial trend of
 198 order k-1 (Chilès and Delfiner, 2012), the core idea behind generalized covariances in geostatistics.
 199 For example (figure 4), considering the differences of differences (increments of order 2), it is possible
 200 to filter out a trend of order 1, i.e., a planar trend in 2D. The modeling of the trend with a simple
 201 planar trend is a reasonable assumption when considering short lag distances. For longer distances
 202 quadratic or cubic surfaces should be considered (Burrough and McDonnel, 1998) and hence higher
 203 order increments.

204
$$D_{D23D12}^{k2} = D_{23}^{k1} - D_{12}^{k1} = (z_2 - z_3) - (z_1 - z_2) = 2z_2 - z_1 - z_3 = [z_1, z_2, z_3]T \cdot [-1, 2, -1]$$

205 *Figure 4. Example (1D) illustrating how the differences of order 2 can be computed with one convolution*
 206 *for lags of 1 px (in the formula T indicates transposition). An analytical example for computing the*
 207 *differences of order 2 centered on the pixel z_2 is shown.*

208
 209 Accordingly, the new TRI_{K2} estimator (in which "K2" is reminiscent of increments of order 2), referring
 210 to the pixel indexing layout of figure 5, is derived with the following pseudocode:

$$\begin{aligned}
 211 \quad TRI_{K2} = & (|-z_1+2z_7 - z_{13}| + |-z_{11}+2z_{12} - z_{13}| + |-z_{21}+2z_{17} - z_{13}| + |-z_{23}+2z_{18} - z_{13}| + \\
 212 \quad & |-z_{25}+2z_{19} - z_{13}| + |-z_{15}+2z_{14} - z_{13}| + |-z_5+2z_9 - z_{13}| + |-z_3+2z_8 - z_{13}| + |-z_7+2z_{13} - \\
 213 \quad & z_{19}| + |-z_{12}+2z_{13} - z_{14}| + |-z_{17}+2z_{13} - z_9| + |-z_{18}+2z_{13} - z_8|)/12 \quad (6)
 \end{aligned}$$

214

1	6	11	16	21
2	7	12	17	22
3	8	13	18	23
4	9	14	19	24
5	10	15	20	25

215
 216 *Figure 5. Pixel indexing layout for a 5x5 kernel adopted for the pseudocode of TRI_{K2}*

217
 218 A graphical representation of the approach is reported in figure 6. It should be noted that TRI_{K2} can
 219 be computed also with a 3x3 kernel (figure 6, orange and red arrows in the central pixel); however,
 220 only 4 DDs of order 2 are used (directions N-S, NE-SW, E-W and SE-NW), leading to a potentially
 221 noisy metric. With the 5x5 kernel, 12 DDs of order 2 are used, leading to larger number of samples
 222 to compute the index and hence more statistical stability respect to the original formulation. As done
 223 for TRI, it is worth noting that, given the layout of figure 6, dividing the DDs of order 1 and 2 by the
 224 lag distance one obtains the (discrete) directional derivatives of order 2 radiating from the central
 225 pixel, and hence there is a relation with the discrete Laplacian operator. Therefore, like the Laplacian
 226 operator, TRI_{K2} is able to detect sharp edges and, in general, high frequency (i.e. short range) features,
 227 which is the case of short-range roughness. Clearly, TRI_{K2} , like the Laplacian, is affected by high-
 228 frequency noise. On the one hand, it is clear that the measurement of a quality such as roughness
 229 requires that noise of comparable frequency, i.e. 1 px^{-1} , be negligible. On the other hand, the fact that
 230 TRI_{K2} comes from the mean of 12 values, each of which corresponds to a 1D discrete Laplacian
 231 operator, as shown in Eq. (6), reduces the effect of noise.

233
 234 *Figure 6. The calculation is performed in one convolution, as in figure 4 for the 1D case; however, for*
 235 *illustrative purposes it can be interpreted as two step-convolution: step 1 (left) computation DDs of order*
 236 *1; step 2, computation of DDs of order 2 from the differences (green squares) computed in step 1. Blue*
 237 *arrows represent directional differences of order 1 with lags of 1 px and the light blue with a lag of $\sqrt{2}$*
 238 *pixels. Red arrows represent directional differences of order 2 with lags of 1 px and the orange with a*
 239 *lag of $\sqrt{2}$ px.*

240
 241 This solution resolves the algorithmic dependency on local slope as shown in figure 7, where it is
 242 applied on the same high-resolution DEM of figure 2. For this DEM, the correlation between TRl_{k2}
 243 and slope is 0.753.

244
 245 *Figure 7. $TR1_{k2}$ can be applied directly to a DEM, the effect of local slope is automatically filtered (color*
 246 *scale histogram equalized).*

247
 248 2.2.2 Radial roughness index

249 The potential bias related to the different lag distances between main directions and the diagonal
 250 ones can be reduced with the same approach adopted by Trevisani et al. 2015, based on bilinear
 251 interpolation. In particular (figure 8) bilinear interpolation is adopted to derive an elevation value at
 252 a distance of 1 px along the diagonals. Accordingly, using the weights of bilinear interpolation is
 253 possible to modify the code for $TR1_{k2}$ so as to calculate the differences at the same 1 px distance in
 254 all directions (figure 8). The modified algorithm is named radial roughness index (RRI) and its

255 formulation (r function RRI()) is fully reported in the shared R code
 256 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7132160>).

257
 258 *Figure 8. Example of computation of DDs of order 2 correcting for the different lag distance between*
 259 *the DD in NS direction (1 px) and NE-SW direction ($\sqrt{2}$ px).*

260
 261 From the visual perspective RRI (figure 9 top) apparently produces the same patterns to TRI_{k2} (figure 9
 262 7); however, in correspondence of anisotropic features there could be marked differences (figure 9
 263 bottom) and most of the time RRI will compute lower values. In fact, for the DEM considered, there
 264 are only 0.2% of cases in which the differences between TRI_{k2} and RRI are lower than -0.02 m. In fact,
 265 RRI will provide lower values than TRI_{k2} in presence of anisotropic features with wavelengths longer
 266 than $2\sqrt{2}$ px in the direction of maximum spatial variability, depending on their orientation; however,
 267 with anisotropic features whose wavelength is shorter than $2\sqrt{2}$ px, depending on their orientation,
 268 RRI could return higher variability than TRI_{k2}.

269
 270 *Figure 9. Short-range radial roughness computed on the high-resolution DEM with the RRI algorithm*
 271 *(top). The differences with TRI_{k2} (bottom) can be relevant in presence of anisotropic features.*

272
 273 Discussion and conclusion

274 The solution provided is simple and easy to implement, and this should be preferred to the well-
 275 known TRI when the focus is on short-range radial roughness without the effect of slope. RRI
 276 minimizes the bias in spatial variability estimation and improves the interpretation of the index, that
 277 now is referred to a 1 px lag. The applications of RRI are analogous to those of TRI, which is a measure
 278 of topographic heterogeneity. However, RRI highlights the effects of short-wavelength terrain
 279 undulations, whereas TRI depends on both local slope and short-wavelength undulations. For the
 280 DEM shown in the figures here, RRI decreases the correlation between TRI and slope from 0.989 to a

281 correlation of 0.753 between RRI and slope; the new name emphasizes that it is a new and
282 independent parameter and not just another measure of slope.

283 From the set of twelve DDs of order 2 (corrected or not for diagonals) one can be tempted to consider
284 other estimators with respect to the mean, such as the median and the minimum. The median could
285 reduce the impact of hotspots and the minimum can be interesting from the ecological perspective,
286 given that very often the governing driver is the lowest impedance found in the surrounding
287 directions. However, the low number of samples limits this kind of application. For example, the
288 adoption of the median as estimator would be analogous to MAD based estimators (Trevisani and
289 Rocca 2015; Trevisani et al., 2023) including MAD_{k2} , the version using increments of order 2. However,
290 for MAD and MAD_{k2} (figure 10 bottom right) a much larger set of DDs is generally used for deriving
291 the indexes of roughness (omnidirectional roughness and anisotropy). With MAD, for statistical
292 reasons, it is suggested to use at least a 5 x 5 window, permitting to select 25 DDs in each of the 4
293 directions (main ones and diagonals); ultimately, for the isotropic short-range roughness 100 DDs are
294 used. MAD approach is more robust to non-stationarity and abrupt transitions (e.g., figure 10).
295 Moreover, this approach permits computing other roughness indexes such as anisotropy and the
296 possibility to select different lag distances.

297 RRI can be considered a valid option as an omnidirectional short-range roughness metric, when the
298 pixel centered perspective is significant for the study at hand; otherwise, the geostatistical estimators
299 provide a more flexible alternative, with a sound theoretical framework. The implemented code and
300 test files (DEM and outputs presented in this note) are available (Trevisani, 2023), promoting the
301 implementation in readers' preferred software.

302 Finally, as far as computational efficiency is concerned, calculating RRI for the DEM considered here
303 (716x943 px) takes 3.46 s with a 3.2 MHz 8th Gen. Intel Core i7 CPU with 16 GB RAM. It is therefore a
304 program that can run on any PC currently available. Moreover, the current implementation can be
305 further improved for computing performance.

306

307
 308 *Figure 10. For a detail of the test area of figure 2, comparison of short-range roughness computed with*
 309 *RRI and with MAD_{k2} (Trevisani et al., 2023). The latter has been computed with a lag of 1 px, with a 3x3*
 310 *(bottom left) and 5x5 (bottom right) square search window. MAD is conceived to be more robust to*
 311 *non-stationarity and abrupt morphological transitions, permitting a sharper representation of*
 312 *roughness.*

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320 References

- 321 Atkinson, P.M. & Lewis, P. 2000. Geostatistical classification for remote sensing: An introduction.
322 Computers and Geosciences, vol. 26, no. 4, pp. 361-371.
- 323 Balaguer, A., Ruiz, L.A., Hermosilla, T., Recio, J.A., 2010. Definition of a Comprehensive set of texture
324 semivariogram features and their evaluation for object-oriented image classification. Computers &
325 Geosciences 36, 231-240.
- 326 Bez, N. & Bertrand, S., 2011. The duality of fractals: Roughness and self-similarity. Theoretical Ecology,
327 vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 371-383.
- 328 Brožová, N., Baggio, T., D'agostino, V., Bühler, Y. & Bebi, P. 2021. Multiscale analysis of surface
329 roughness for the improvement of natural hazard modelling. Natural Hazards and Earth System
330 Sciences, 21 (11), 3539-3562.
- 331 Burrough, P.A. & McDonnell, R.A. 1998. Principles of Geographical Information Systems. Oxford
332 University Press Oxford.
- 333 Cavalli, M., Marchi, L., 2008. Characterisation of the surface morphology of an alpine alluvial fan using
334 airborne LiDAR. Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences 8, 323–333.
- 335 Chilès, J.-P., Delfiner, P., 2012. Geostatistics - Modeling Spatial Uncertainty. John Wiley & Sons, Inc.,
336 New Jersey.
- 337 Frankel, K.L., Dolan, J.F., 2007. Characterizing arid-region alluvial fan surface roughness with airborne
338 laser swath mapping digital topographic data, Journal of Geophysical Research – Earth Surface 112,
339 F02025, doi:10.1029/2006JF000644.
- 340 Garrigues, S., Allard, D., Baret, F., Weiss, M., 2006. Quantifying spatial heterogeneity at the landscape
341 scale using variogram models. Remote Sensing of Environment 103, 81-96.
- 342 Glenn, N.F., Streutker, D.R., Chadwick, D.J., Thackray, G.D., Dorsch, S.J., 2006. Analysis of LiDAR-
343 derived topographic information for characterizing and differentiating landslide morphology and
344 activity. Geomorphology 73, 131-148.
- 345 Goovaerts, P., 1997. Geostatistics for Natural Resources Evaluation. Oxford University Press, Oxford.
- 346 Grohmann, C.H., Smith, M.J., Riccomini, C., 2011. Multiscale Analysis of Topographic Surface
347 Roughness in the Midland Valley, Scotland. IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing
348 49, 1220-1213.
- 349 Guisan, A., Weiss, S.B. & Weiss, A.D. 1999. GLM versus CCA spatial modeling of plant species
350 distribution. Plant Ecology, vol. 143, no. 1, pp. 107-122.
- 351 Guth, P.L., 1999. Quantifying Topographic Fabric: Eigenvector Analysis Using Digital Elevation Models.
352 In 27th Applied Imagery Pattern Recognition (AIPR) Workshop: Advances in Computer-Assisted

353 Recognition, 14-16 Oct 1988, Washington, DC, R.J. Merisko, ed., Proceedings of SPIE [The International
354 Society for Optical Engineering] vol.3584, p.233-243.

355 Guth, P.L., 2001. Quantifying terrain fabric in digital elevation models. In Ehlen, J., and Harmon, R.S.,
356 eds., The environmental legacy of military operations, Geological Society of America Reviews in
357 Engineering Geology, vol, 14, chapter 3, p.13-25.

358 Guth, P. & Kane, M. 2021. Slope, aspect, and hillshade algorithms for non-square digital elevation
359 models. Transactions in GIS, vol. 25, no. 5, pp. 2309-2332.

360 Hagerty, B.E., Nussear, K.E., Esque, T.C., Tracy, C.R., 2011. Making molehills out of mountains:
361 Landscape genetics of the Mojave desert tortoise. Landscape Ecology, 26 (2), pp. 267-280.

362 Haralick, R.M., Dinstein, I. & Shanmugam, K., 1973. Textural Features for Image Classification. IEEE
363 Transactions on Systems, Man and Cybernetics, vol. SMC-3, no. 6, pp. 610-621.

364 Herzfeld, U.C., Higginson, C.A., 1996. Automated geostatistical seafloor classification - Principles,
365 parameters, feature vectors, and discrimination criteria. Computers and Geosciences, 22 (1), pp. 35-
366 52.

367 Isaaks, E.H., Srivastava, R.M. 1989. An Introduction to Applied Geostatistics. Oxford University Press:
368 New York, NY, USA.

369 Jenness, J.S. 2004. Calculating landscape surface area from digital elevation models. Wildlife Society
370 Bulletin, vol. 32, no. 3, pp. 829-839.

371 Leach, R., (editor) 2013. Characterisation of areal surface texture. Springer Heidelberg New York
372 Dordrecht London 355 pp, DOI 10.1007/978-3-642-36458-7.

373 Lindsay, J.B., Newman, D.R. & Francioni, A., 2019. Scale-optimized surface roughness for topographic
374 analysis. Geosciences (Switzerland), vol. 9, no. 7.

375 Lucieer, A., Stein, A., 2005. Texture-based landform segmentation of LiDAR imagery. International
376 Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation 6, 261-270.

377 McKean, J., Roering, J., 2004. Objective landslide detection and surface morphology mapping using
378 high-resolution airborne laser altimetry. Geomorphology 57, 331-351.

379 Nellemann, C. & Thomsen, M.G. 1994. Terrain ruggedness and caribou forage availability during
380 snowmelt on the Arctic coastal plain, Alaska. Arctic, vol. 47, no. 4, pp. 361-367.

381 Newman, D.R., Cockburn, J.M.H., Dragut, L., Lindsay, J.B., 2022. Evaluating Scaling Frameworks for
382 Multiscale Geomorphometric Analysis. Geomatics 2022, 2, 36-51. <https://doi.org/10.3390/>

383 Ojala, T., Pietikäinen, M., Mäenpää, T., 2002. Multiresolution gray-scale and rotation invariant texture
384 classification with local binary patterns. IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine
385 Intelligence, 24 (7), pp. 971-987.

386 Pike, R.J., 2000. Geomorphometry – diversity in quantitative surface analysis. Progress in Physical
387 Geography 24, 1-20.

388 Pollyea, R.M. & Fairley, J.P., 2011. Estimating surface roughness of terrestrial laser scan data using
389 orthogonal distance regression. Geology, vol. 39, no. 7, pp. 623-626.

390 R Development Core Team, 2009. R: A language and environment for statistical computing. R
391 Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria.

392 Riley, S. J., S. D. DeGloria, and R. Elliott. 1999. A terrain ruggedness index that quantifies topographic
393 heterogeneity. Intermountain Journal of Science 5:23–27.

394 Różycka, M., Migoń, P., Michniewicz, A., 2017. Topographic Wetness Index and Terrain Ruggedness
395 Index in geomorphic characterisation of landslide terrains, on examples from the Sudetes, SW Poland.
396 Zeitschrift für Geomorphologie, Supplementary Issues, 61(2), 61–80.

397 Sappington, J.M., Longshore, K.M. & Thompson, D.B. 2007. Quantifying landscape ruggedness for
398 animal habitat analysis: A case study using bighorn sheep in the Mojave Desert. Journal of Wildlife
399 Management, vol. 71, no. 5, pp. 1419-1426.

400 Shepard, M.K., Campbell, B.A., Bulmer, M.H., Farr, T.G., Gaddis, L.R. & Plaut, J.J., 2001. The roughness
401 of natural terrain: A planetary and remote sensing perspective. Journal of Geophysical Research E:
402 Planets, vol. 106, no. E12, pp. 32777-32795.

403 Smith, M.W., 2014. Roughness in the Earth Sciences. Earth-Science Reviews, vol. 136, pp. 202-225.

404 Trevisani, S., Cavalli, M., Marchi, L., 2009. Variogram maps from LiDAR data as fingerprints of surface
405 morphology on scree slopes. Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences 9, 129–133.

406 Trevisani, S., Cavalli, M. & Marchi, L. 2010. Reading the bed morphology of a mountain stream: A
407 geomorphometric study on high-resolution topographic data. Hydrology and Earth System Sciences,
408 vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 393-405.

409 Trevisani, S., Cavalli, M. & Marchi, L. 2012. Surface texture analysis of a high-resolution DTM:
410 Interpreting an alpine basin. Geomorphology, vol. 161-162, pp. 26-39.

411 Trevisani, S. & Rocca, M., 2015. MAD: Robust image texture analysis for applications in high resolution
412 geomorphometry. Computers and Geosciences, vol. 81, pp. 78-92.

413 Trevisani, S. & Cavalli, M., 2016. Topography-based flow-directional roughness: Potential and
414 challenges. Earth Surface Dynamics, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 343-358.

415 Trevisani, S., Teza, G. & Guth, P., 2023. A Simplified Geostatistical Approach for Characterizing Key
416 Aspects of Short-Range Roughness. Catena, Volume 223,
417 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2023.106927>.

418 Vukomanovic, J., Orr, B.J., 2014. Landscape Aesthetics and the Scenic Drivers of Amenity Migration in
419 the New West: Naturalness, Visual Scale, and Complexity. *Land*, 3(2): 390-413.
420 <https://doi.org/10.3390/land3020390>.

421 Wilson, J.P., Gallant J.C. (editors) 2000. *Terrain Analysis: Principles and Applications*. Wiley, 520 pp.

422 Wilson, M.F.J., O'Connell, B., Brown, C., Guinan, J.C. & Grehan, A.J. 2007, "Multiscale terrain analysis
423 of multibeam bathymetry data for habitat mapping on the continental slope", *Marine Geodesy*, vol.
424 30, no. 1-2, pp. 3-35.

425 Woodcock, N.H., 1977. Specification of fabric shapes using an eigenvalue method: *Geological Society
426 of America Bulletin*, vol.88, p.1231-1236.

427 Woodcock, C.E., Strahler, A.H. & Jupp, D.L.B., 1988. The use of variograms in remote sensing: II. Real
428 digital images. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, vol. 25, no. 3, pp. 349-379.

429

430

431 Web references

432 ESRI, 2023. ArcGIS home page. [https://www.esri.com/en-us/arcgis/products/arcgis-
433 desktop/resources](https://www.esri.com/en-us/arcgis/products/arcgis-

433 desktop/resources) (accessed 1 March 2023)

434 GRASS, 2023. GRASS GIS home page. <https://grass.osgeo.org/> (accessed 1 March 2023)

435 Guth, P.L, 2023, MICRODEM github. https://github.com/prof-pguth/git_microdem (accessed 8 March
436 2023)

437 Ilich, Alexander R.; Misiuk, Benjamin; Lecours, Vincent; Murawski, Steven A.; 2021. MultiscaleDTM
438 download page. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5548338>. <https://github.com/ailich/MultiscaleDTM>
439 (accessed: 1 March 2023).

440 RSPATIAL, 2023. Terra package for R home page. <https://rspatial.org/terra/> (accessed 1 March 2023):

441 SAGA, 2023. SAGA GIS home page. <https://saga-gis.sourceforge.io/en/index.html> (accessed 1 March
442 2023)

443 Trevisani S. 2023. Software code: "MADSurfaceTexture", "SurfRough" package, download page.
444 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7132160> (accessed 1 March 2023)

445 USNA, 2023. MICRODEM mapping program home page.
446 <https://www.usna.edu/Users/oceano/pguth/website/microdem/microdem.htm> (accessed 1 March
447 2023).

448 Whitebox Geospatial, 2023. Whitebox home page. <https://www.whiteboxgeo.com/> (accessed 1 March
449 2023)